

Supplementary Materials

Pilot data

Figure S1 shows our proposed analyses (replicating Figures 4-5 from Ozaki et al. (2024)) for the same pilot experiment shown in Savage et al.'s Figure 4 (Savage et al., (2025) (i.e., $n=14$ participants from Auckland, New Zealand singing/speaking in English in three groups of 4-5 people at a time in June/July 2024). Note that these pilot experiments will not be used for confirmatory analyses in Stage 2 reports resulting from either ref. (Savage et al., 2025) or the current protocol - they are only used for pilot analyses.

Notably, all of the 14 participants produced enough analyseable data of high enough quality that no participants had to be excluded. This suggests that the various changes made from Ozaki et al.'s (2024) design (e.g., a single microphone recording multiple individuals engaged in alternating singing/free conversation) did not compromise our ability to accurately replicate their analyses. The general trends (i.e., song again appearing higher, slower, and more stable than speech) also indicate that any changes in experimental design are unlikely to result in major changes to results.

Although we do not want to over-interpret minor differences in pilot data, we do note that, while the mean effect size for temporal rate (translated Cohen's $D=1.8$) is quite similar to Ozaki et al.'s (2024) ($D=1.6$), the effect sizes for pitch height ($D=0.8$) and pitch stability ($D=0.4$) appear somewhat smaller than the original analysis ($D=1.6$ and $D=0.7$, respectively; see Table S1). While any such differences that may arise in our Stage 2 data could reflect normal variation, they could also reflect systematic differences such as language-specific effects, differences in musical training of participants, or the fact that unlike Ozaki et al.'s (2024) design, singing in a group context (even when each singer sings one solo line at a time) usually results in all singers matching their singing to a single shared key (tonal centre), which may not have been the one best suited to the natural range of all singers' voices. These possibilities (and others, such as potential order effects described in the "Randomisation" section above) may be worth addressing in the Discussion section and Exploratory Analysis sections of the resulting Stage 2 reports.

Figure S1 - Pilot analyses replicating analyses of pitch height, temporal rate, and pitch stability (cf. Ozaki et al. (2024) Figures 4-5) for 14 pilot participants singing/conversing in English in Auckland, New Zealand (cf. Savage et al. (2025) Figure 4).

Feature	Original effect size	Pilot effect size
Pitch height	1.6	0.8
Temporal rate	1.6	1.8
Pitch stability	0.7	0.4

Table S1 - Comparison of effect sizes (translated Cohen's *D*) for the three proposed features from Ozaki et al.'s (2024) original study ($n=75$ participants (Ozaki et al., 2024)) with pilot data from the current protocol ($n=14$ participants from Savage et al., 2025)

Inter-rater reliability

Figure S2 - Distributions of onset time differences between the two annotators (Jia and Savage) for annotating participant 19. The left panel shows onset time differences for the conversation annotation ($n = 38$ syllables; mean \pm SD = 0.19 ± 0.18 s; intraclass correlation > 0.99 , $p < 1 \times 10^{-16}$), and the right panel shows those for the singing annotation ($n = 25$ notes; mean \pm SD = 0.13 ± 0.07 s; intraclass correlation > 0.99 , $p = .00006$).